

CAUSES OF TEACHERS' JOB STRESS IN PRIVATE SCHOOLS AND COPING STRATEGIES

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Abstract

This research was intended to identify the causes of job stress in private schools and coping strategies. The main objectives of the study were 1) to identify the causes of teachers' job stress in private schools, 2) to compare the causes of job stress across gender and 3) to find out the coping strategies for job stress in private schools. The design of this investigation was a sequential-explanatory mixed method design to investigate the causes of teachers' job stress in private schools and explore the coping strategies to reduce the job stress. The target population of the study was comprised of all teachers both male and female in private schools of Town 2, district Peshawar. The tools of the study were questionnaire and interview. The tools were subjected to pilot testing before administration in the field. It is evident from the findings that teachers at private schools are suffering from job stress, physically, socially and psychologically. In order to cope with job stress, the respondents viewed that these should be adequate workload, adequate policies for promotion, leaves, salaries etc. teachers should be involved in decision making. Similarly, there should be no favoritism. The environment should be of mutual respect and motivating. Teachers may be given organizational support by revising policies regarding leave, teachers' induction, promotion, expulsion etc. the study recommended adequate measures to cope with physical and administrative, social and psychological factors of job stress.

1. Introduction

The constantly changing and developing world brings new demands and challenges in all walks and professions of life. In past, teachers were just concerned to deliver some useful content to students just through verbal deliver of content. Now a days, teachers have to teach diverse skills, contents and techniques aligning with the socio-emotional development of students. This is an

era of competition in all walks of life including education. In the field of education, this race is more evident among private schools. In order to be in race, every school makes diverse efforts for good performance. These competitions increase the workload and stress of teachers. The have to keeping in view the demands and wishes of school administrators, parents, society and other social organization and bodies associated with

education. Besides, they are facing the issue of underemployment, rigid time tables, and tough deadlines

Besides, their routine works, teachers are confronted with extra works, non-teaching assignments, enormous workload, tough deadlines, work pressure, tense school environment, poor wages and job insecurity etc. These issues have increased the amount of job stress for teachers. The stress affects them mentally, socially and psychologically. The job stress not only affect the teachers personally but also have subsequent effects on their students and quality of instruction (Banal & Ortega-Dela, 2022; Shah, 2023). The literature indicates that enormous workload is a vital reason of teacher stress, results in burnout, poor job performance, and increased rates of turnover (Gupta & Rani, 2014; Jain & Cooper, 2012). It is imperative to consider the issue of teachers in private schools. This study has highlighted the various dimension of job stress in private schools along with measures for coping.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the causes of teachers' job stress in private schools
- To compare the causes of job stress across gender
- To find out the coping strategies for job stress in private schools

2. Review of the Related Literature

Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, developed by Demerouti et al. (2001), is widely used to explain workplace stress and burnout. This model divides work-related factors into two categories: job demands and job resources. The JD-R model provides a theoretical framework for understanding the causes of stress in private school teachers. The model suggests that job stress arises from the imbalance between job demands and job resources. When job demands exceed job resources, teachers experience stress, which can lead to burnout, absenteeism, and turnover.

Job demands refer to the aspects of a job that require effort and can lead to physical and emotional exhaustion if not managed properly. Examples include long working hours, high workloads, unclear job roles, and strained relationships with colleagues or supervisors (Demerouti & Bakker, 2011). While job demands are not inherently negative, they become stressors when teachers feel incapable of meeting expectations. In contrast, job resources are elements that help teachers accomplish their tasks effectively and reduce job-related stress. These include adequate salaries, job security, access to teaching materials, supportive colleagues, and opportunities for professional growth (Demerouti & Bakker, 2011; Jain & Cooper, 2012).

Teacher Workload and Stress

Teaching is often regarded as one of the most rewarding yet demanding professions. Teachers are entrusted with the responsibility of shaping young minds, but this noble task comes with significant challenges. Teacher workload refers to the multitude of tasks teachers handle, such as preparing lessons, grading assignments, managing classroom behavior, and organizing extracurricular activities. According to Kyriacou (2001), excessive workload can lead to both physical and emotional exhaustion, ultimately affecting teachers' health and job performance. Stress emerges when teachers feel overwhelmed by the demands of their role, leaving them with insufficient time and resources to manage their responsibilities effectively.

Collie et al. (2012) highlighted that stress among teachers is often triggered by factors such as disruptive student behavior, lack of administrative support, and difficulties in maintaining a healthy work-life balance. When teachers feel unsupported or unappreciated, their stress levels tend to rise, impacting their ability to teach effectively.

Banal and Ortega-Dela (2022) pointed out that private school teachers often experience additional pressures due to high expectations from school administrators and parents. These

expectations create an environment where teachers feel the need to constantly prove their competence, leading to heightened stress and burnout. Shah et al. (2023) emphasized that the heavy workload and excessive paperwork associated with private schools contribute significantly to teacher stress levels. Similarly, Gupta and Rani (2014) argued that stress often results when school management fails to provide adequate support to meet teachers' personal and professional needs.

The stress experienced by teachers does not exist in isolation; it has ripple effects that influence the entire learning environment. When teachers are overburdened, their energy, creativity, and enthusiasm often diminish, affecting their performance and interaction with students. Studies have indicated that stressed teachers are more likely to face burnout, suffer from emotional exhaustion, and even consider leaving the profession altogether (Banal & Ortega-Dela, 2022; Shah, 2023). Such challenges are particularly prominent in private schools, where teachers often face higher expectations from parents and administrators to produce exceptional academic outcomes. These pressures create a competitive environment that can leave teachers feeling undervalued and unsupported.

Comparison between Private and Public School Environments

Teachers in private schools face distinct challenges compared to their counterparts in public schools. Dinham and Scott (2000) noted that private school teachers generally earn lower salaries and face greater job insecurity, which can lead to increased stress levels. On the other hand, private schools often have smaller class sizes, which may create a more manageable teaching environment and reduce certain stressors.

Despite these advantages, research consistently highlights the intense pressure faced by private school teachers to meet high academic standards and parental expectations. Hakanen et al. (2006) found a direct link between heavy workloads and teacher stress, showing that unmanageable

workloads often lead to burnout, job dissatisfaction, and even high turnover rates.

To address these challenges, Greenberg et al. (2016) suggested that schools adopt strategies such as time management training, sharing administrative tasks, and offering professional development programs. These interventions can help alleviate stress and improve teachers' overall well-being.

Strategies for Workload Management

Managing teacher workloads effectively is crucial for reducing stress and improving job satisfaction. Greenberg et al. (2016) proposed several strategies to achieve this goal. First, time management training can help teachers prioritize tasks and stay organized. Delegating non-teaching duties, such as administrative tasks, can also free up valuable time for teachers to focus on instructional activities.

Professional development programs can empower teachers by enhancing their skills and boosting their confidence. Moreover, administrative support plays a key role in reducing stress by acknowledging teachers' hard work and addressing their concerns promptly. Schools can also foster a collaborative culture where teachers share responsibilities and support each other. Similarly, Mentorship programs and peer networks can further ease the burden on teachers by promoting teamwork and shared accountability (Renshaw & Cooper, 2006). Creating a positive work environment where teachers feel valued and supported can significantly enhance their well-being.

3. Method and Procedure

The design for this research was sequential-explanatory mixed method to explore the causes of stress at working environment in private schools for teachers. It was also intended to highlight the strategies which are beneficial in reducing the level stress at a work in environment.

For quantitative phase, data were accumulated through a questionnaire of 4-point Likert Scale. The questionnaire was consisted of 3 sections i.e.,

‘physical and administrative’ factors, social factors and psychological factors of job stress. For qualitative phase, to identify coping strategies to reduce stress at working environment, the researcher conducted an interview from 10 participants. The interview addressed the coping strategies encompassing all the broad areas job stress.

The population of this investigation included all male and female teachers of private schools in Town 2 of district Peshawar. There were 76 properly registered private school in Town-2, Peshawar as per gazette book of Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education - 2023 (BISE, 2023). Due to resources constraints of

resource, time and some administrative issues, led the researchers to delimit his investigation to 30 schools in private sector through cluster sampling. Further, teachers from both primary and secondary levels were taken.

4. Results

The quantitative data were analyzed through mean and standard deviation for description of data. Similarly, one sample t-test and independent sample t-tests were employed to get valid inferences from the data. Similarly, the qualitative data were collected in the form of notes. It was then coded, categorized and then the themes were emerged from it.

Table 1. Overall Mean Distribution of Physical and Administrative Factors of Job Stress

Job Stress Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
High work load	3.09	.979
Rigid time table	3.02	1.037
No free period	2.82	1.082
non-teaching assignments	2.50	1.029
extra work	3.04	.965
working after school hours	2.79	1.144
strict discipline for teachers	3.10	.982
disciplinary problems of students	2.68	1.069
students' poor performance	3.03	.965
strict leave rules	3.14	.938
poor promotion policy	3.18	1.053
amount of salary	3.12	.975

Table 1 shows higher mean values almost on all aspects which indicate that majority of teachers are confronted with stress due to physical and administrative problems. The highest mean score is carried by the poor promotion policy (M = 3.18, SD = 1.053). Other high means values are carried by high work load (M = 3.09), rigid time table (M = 3.02), extra work (M = 3.04), strict

discipline for teachers (M = 3.14) and amount of salary (M = 3.12). The lowest mean score (M = 2.50) is carried by the non-teaching assignments. It can be concluded that almost the majority of private school teachers suffered job stress due to physical and administrative dimension of job stress.

Table 2. Overall Mean Distribution of Social Factors of Job Stress

Social Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
Overall attitude of the principal	2.96	1.141
one way communication	2.77	1.113
Non-supporting environment	2.82	1.061
Lack of motivation	2.76	1.037

Unhealthy competitions among teachers	2.71	1.118
Favouritism by head of Institute	2.82	1.115
Conflict with parents	2.34	1.096
Unhealthy criticism by head and staff members	2.81	1.117
Negative comments by peers	2.32	1.100
Hypocrisy	3.02	1.069

The data in Table 2 indicate the distribution of social factors of job stress. On all descriptions the mean values are relatively higher. The highest mean value is carried by hypocrisy (M = 3.02) in school environments. Likewise, the overall attitude of the head of institute is also a major factor of job stress have mean score of (M = 2.81). Similarly, non-supporting environment and

favouritism by head of the institutes carries equal mean value (M = 2.82). Further, unhealthy criticism (M = 2.81), one way communication M = 2.77) and lack of motivation M = 2.76) are other importance factors of job stress. The lowest mean score is carried by negative comment by peers M = 2.32).

Table 3. Mean Distribution of Psychological Factors of Job Stress

Psychological Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
High work pressure	3.17	1.110
tough deadlines	2.97	1.065
No job security	3.32	1.047
Threatening environment	2.96	1.088
Excessive restrictions	2.99	.974
Lack of support	2.88	1.073
Feeling insecure	3.02	1.152

It is evident from Table 3 that almost on all descriptions, the mean values are quite higher. No job security carries the highest mean value (M = 3.32). Similarly, high work pressure (M = 3.17) and feelings of insecurity (M = 3.02) also carries relatively higher mean scores. Further, tough deadlines (M = 2.97), threatening environment (M = 2.96) and excessive restrictions (M = 2.99) are also elements of higher concern. Of all the smallest mean value is associated with lack of

support (2.82). Hence, it can be drawn that almost on all items of psychological factor, the higher mean values indicate that psychological factors are vital to job stress.

Gender Comparison

Gender comparison was carried for each statement to determine whether is there any differences in the views of male and female respondents.

Table 4. Comparing the Physical and Administrative Factors across Gender

Physical and Administrative Factors	Test of equality of means			
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
High work load	-1.788	118	.076	-.317
	-1.788	108.689	.076	-.317
Rigid time table	-1.057	118	.293	-.200
	-1.057	117.700	.293	-.200
No free period	-2.141	118	.034	-.417
	-2.141	116.683	.034	-.417

non-teaching assignments	-1.975	118	.051	-.367
	-1.975	116.004	.051	-.367
extra work	-1.041	118	.300	-.183
	-1.041	106.591	.300	-.183
working after school hours	-2.876	118	.005	-.583
	-2.876	115.724	.005	-.583
strict discipline for teachers	-.185	118	.853	-.033
	-.185	117.180	.853	-.033
discipline problems of students	1.371	118	.173	.267
	1.371	117.038	.173	.267
students' poor performance	1.232	118	.220	.217
	1.232	112.742	.221	.217
strict leave rules	.485	118	.628	.083
	.485	117.663	.628	.083
poor promotion policy	-3.642	118	.000	-.667
	-3.642	103.349	.000	-.667
amount of salary	-2.998	118	.003	-.517
	-2.998	117.188	.003	-.517

Table 4 indicates the t-test analyses for each of the statement to trace significant difference in the views of male and female respondents. There is significant difference on the views of respondents on the provision of free periods as indicated by the t-test ($t(118) = -2.141, p = .0034 < .05$). Similarly, for working after school hours, there is significant differences as indicated by ($t(118) = -2.876, p = .0005 < .05$). It can be drawn that

female teachers are more concerned about it. Further, the t-test values ($t(118) = -3.642, p = .0000 < .05$) indicate considerable differences on poor promotion policy. Finally, on amount of salary, worthwhile differences could be seen ($t(118) = -2.998, p = .0003 < .05$). It means that female teachers in private schools have serious issues with their salary.

Table 5. Comparing the Social Factor of Job Stress across Gender

Test of equality of means				
Social Factor	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Overall attitude of the principal	-.399	118	.691	-.083
	-.399	114.611	.691	-.083
one way communication	-2.692	118	.008	-.533
	-2.692	117.995	.008	-.533
Non-supporting environment	-4.019	118	.000	-.733
	-4.019	115.899	.000	-.733
Lack of motivation	-2.806	118	.006	-.517
	-2.806	114.156	.006	-.517
Unhealthy competitions among teachers	-4.082	118	.000	-.783

	-4.082	117.911	.000	-.783
Favouritism by head of Institute	-2.335	118	.021	-.467
	-2.335	115.747	.021	-.467
Conflict with parents	-1.422	118	.158	-.283
	-1.422	115.966	.158	-.283
Unhealthy criticism by head and staff members	-3.505	118	.001	-.683
	-3.505	117.655	.001	-.683
Negative comments by peers	-2.547	118	.012	-.500
	-2.547	117.690	.012	-.500
Hypocrisy	-2.625	118	.010	-.500
	-2.625	110.696	.010	-.500

It is evident from the data in Table 6 that on many facets of social factor of job stress although both male and female provide higher mean scores. Yet there are considerable differences in the views of male and female respondents. There is significant differences of the views on one way communication (t (118) = -2.692, p = .0008 < .05), non-supporting environment (t (118) = -4.019, p = .0000 < .05), lack of motivation (t

(118) = -2.806, p = .0006 < .05), unhealthy competitions among staff members (t (118) = -4.082, p = .0000 < .05), favoritism by head teachers unhealthy criticism (t (118) = -2.335, p = .0021 < .05), negative comments by peers (t (118) = -2.517, p = .012 < .05) and hypocrisy (t (118) = -2.625, p = .010 < .05). It can be drawn that female teachers were anxious about these social issues.

Table 6. Comparing the Psychological Factor of Job Stress across Gender

Test of equality of means				
Psychological Factor	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
High work pressure	-1.998	118	.048	-.400
	-1.998	112.949	.048	-.400
tough deadlines	-1.464	118	.146	-.283
	-1.464	115.333	.146	-.283
No job security	-1.850	118	.067	-.350
	-1.850	106.979	.067	-.350
Threatening environment	-1.953	118	.053	-.383
	-1.953	112.867	.053	-.383
Excessive restrictions	-1.220	118	.225	-.217
	-1.220	104.094	.225	-.217
Lack of support	-1.803	118	.074	-.350
	-1.803	108.384	.074	-.350
Feeling insecure	-2.943	118	.004	-.600

Test of equality of means				
Psychological Factor	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
High work pressure	-1.998	118	.048	-.400
	-1.998	112.949	.048	-.400
tough deadlines	-1.464	118	.146	-.283
	-1.464	115.333	.146	-.283
No job security	-1.850	118	.067	-.350
	-1.850	106.979	.067	-.350
Threatening environment	-1.953	118	.053	-.383
	-1.953	112.867	.053	-.383
Excessive restrictions	-1.220	118	.225	-.217
	-1.220	104.094	.225	-.217
Lack of support	-1.803	118	.074	-.350
	-1.803	108.384	.074	-.350
Feeling insecure	-2.943	118	.004	-.600
	-2.943	114.639	.004	-.600

The data in table 6 reveals the differences on psychological dimension of job stress. There is worthwhile difference in views of male and female teachers regarding high work pressure as indicated by the t-test ($t(118) = -1.998, p = .048$

$< .05$). Similarly, there is also considerable difference on the 'feeling insecure' ($t(118) = -2.943, p = .004 < .05$). It can be drawn that there is no much difference in male and female on psychological dimension.

Overall mean values

Table 7. Comparing Means of Overall Facets in Gender Perspective Group Statistics

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Physical and administrative factors	Male	60	2.79	.970	.125
	Female	60	3.02	.842	.109
social factors	Male	60	2.45	1.050	.136
	Female	60	2.96	.938	.121
psychological factors	Male	60	2.86	1.125	.145
	Female	60	3.23	.856	.111

The overall means of the three broad dimensions of job stress are shown in the Table 7. On physical and administrative aspect, the mean value for the male teachers is ($M = 2.79, SD = 0.970$), while for female teachers it is ($M = 3.02, SD = 0.842$). Similarly, for social factor, the mean

values for male are ($M = 2.45, SD = 1.050$) and female respondents are ($M = 2.96, SD = 0.938$). Finally, on psychological facet, the mean score for male is ($M = 2.86, SD = 1.125$) and female is ($M = 3.23, SD = 0.856$). Both, male and female respondents have highest scores on psychological

factor as compared to physical and social facets. Similarly, female students have higher means scores on all three aspects as compared to male

respondents. It can be drawn that female students have higher job stress as compared to male.

Table 8. Comparing overall facets across gender

	Test of equality of means			
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Physical and administrative factors	-1.374	118	.172	-.228
	-1.374	115.703	.172	-.228
social factors	-2.796	118	.006	-.508
	-2.796	116.520	.006	-.508
psychological factors	-2.022	118	.045	-.369
	-2.022	110.191	.046	-.369

The t-test was also conducted to analyze whether differences across gender are significant. The value of t-test ($t(118) = -1.374, p = 0.172 > .05$), which reveals that there is no considerable difference between the views of male and female teachers regarding the physical and administrative aspects of job stress. On, social aspect the value of t-test ($t(118) = -2.796, p = .0006 < .05$), which indicate a significant difference. Similarly, on psychological factors the t-test ($t(118) = -2.022, p = .045 < .05$) (Table 8). It also reveals that there are worthwhile variations in the views of male and female teachers on psychological factors. It can be concluded that female teachers feel higher level job stress on the social and psychological dimensions.

Qualitative Data Analysis

The qualitative data were coded and categorized and then the themes were emerged from it.

Theme 1: Workload Management

The respondent viewed that the strategies may be explored to reduce to workload from teacher. It may be carried through reducing number of classes per day, reducing or eliminating extra academic tasks, rearrangement of certain administrative and administrative tasks such daily assignments and checking of homework, dealing disciplinary issues, carrying clerical tasks etc.

Theme 2: Organizational Support and Policy Change

Leave policy may be changes or it may in accordance with leave rules for public schools. There should be some policy for teacher induction, promotion, expulsion and job security. Teachers may be recruited at least from one to three years. Restrictions should not be imposed on teachers for applying and recruiting in other institutes.

Theme 3: Salary and Incentives

There should be a consistent policy for teachers' salaries and incentives. They should be paid adequate salaries with annual increments etc. similarly, deductions should not be made on extra leaves, and late coming etc. They may also be paid with for performing extra works, working after school hours or on off days. Teachers with good performance may be rewarded time and again. The teachers may be registered with social welfare department.

Theme 4: Respect and well being

Teacher should be provided with due respect. They should not be scolded in front of others. There mistake should be tackled politely. There should be no way communication. Teachers may be involved in decision making at various levels.

Theme 5: socially supporting environment

Teachers should be provided an environment of mutual support, satisfaction and motivation. There should be no unhealthy criticism. The head of institute should no give undue favour to anyone. Similarly, gender bias should be avoided. Conflict among teachers should be resolved in time and with justice. Similarly, mostly issues with parent should be tackled by the head teachers themselves.

Theme 5: Psychologically sound environment:

Every teacher has his own personal psyche and home background. Teachers should be provided with much tough deadlines and workload that they may feel high work pressure and overwhelmed. Necessary steps may be taken to reduce the pressures on teaches as well as their personal anxieties. Excessive restrictions should not be imposed upon teachers. They may not be blamed for students' failure or in-competencies. They should be supported and encouraged.

5. Findings and Conclusions

It is evident from the findings of the study that teachers at private schools are suffering from job stress. On physical and administrative dimensions, the teachers declared that high work load is one of the major causes of job stress. Besides rigid time table, extra works, no free periods, working after school hours and poor salary were the physical cause of job stress. Likewise, strict discipline for teachers, strict leave rules, poor promotion policy were the administrative causes of job stress. In social domain, the autocratic attitudes of the heads of the institutes were one of the major reasons of job stress. Similarly, the schools' environments were not supporting and lacking motivation. Teachers experience their unhealthy criticism from the heads as well as from the colleagues. Further, the heads show favoritism for some teachers which turns the other into frustration. In addition, often they have conflict with parents. Finally, they declared the entire environment suffocated with hypocrisy. it can be drawn that the social causes of job stress are multi-

dimensional i.e. from heads, colleagues and parents

There are some psychological causes of job stress as declared by the teachers. The major problems are high work pressure and tough deadlines. Often teachers have to complete the tasks on time and on daily bases in accordance to given tough deadlines. Another reason is that teacher feels insecure due to threatening environment. Teachers also feel stressed due to threatening environment. In addition, the teachers declared that there is lack of support.

In gender perspective, the views of respondents were congruent in gender perspective. Both male and female shows high concerns on all the dimensions of job stress. However, on some issues there are differences on many elements of job stress. There were significant difference on the views of respondents on the provision of free periods, working after school hours, on poor promotion policy and amount of salary. It means that female teachers in private schools have serious concerns regarding free periods, duty after hours, promotion and salary. In terms of social factors of job stress, yet there are considerable differences on one way communication, non-supporting environment, lack of motivation, unhealthy competitions among staff members, favoritism by head teachers, unhealthy criticism, negative comments by peers and hypocrisy. It can be drawn that female teachers were highly anxious about these social issues. On psychological dimension of job stress, there is worthwhile difference in views of male and female teachers regarding high work pressure and feeling insecure. It can be drawn that there is no much difference in male and female on psychological dimension. Further, female teachers feel high pressure and insecurity.

On the composite means of physical and administrative dimension, both, male and female respondents have highest scores on psychological factor as compared to physical and social facets. Similarly, female students have higher means scores on all three aspects as compared to male respondents. It can be drawn that female students have higher job stress as compared to

male. Comparing overall means across gender indicate non-significant variations for physical and administrative facet. On the contrary, significant variations on social and psychological dimension indicate that female teachers were more caution and conference about these issues of job stress. Similarly, teachers at secondary level were more concerned about these issues.

In order to cope with job stress in private schools, the respondents viewed that these should be adequate workload for the teachers. They may not be subjected to excessive or extra academic and/or official assignments. Teachers may be given organizational support by revising policies regarding leave, teachers' induction, promotion, expulsion etc. There should be a consistent policy for teachers' salaries, incentives and increments. Reward and penalty should be carried with justice. Teacher should be provided with due respect and care. They should be actively involved in decision making and their suggestions should be considered. Teachers should be provided an environment of mutual support, satisfaction and motivation. There should be no unhealthy criticism, injustice, blaming and favoritism. Every teacher has his own personal psyche and home background. Teachers should not overburden tough deadlines, unnecessary workload, file work etc. Necessary steps may be taken to reduce the pressures on teaches by providing them support, encouragement and flexibility.

6. Recommendations

- There may be an adequate academic workload for teachers. There may be an adequate number of periods, with the elimination of extra work, academic assignments, and administrative affairs.
- Teachers may be given organizational support by revising policies regarding leave, teachers' induction, promotion, expulsion etc.
- There may be a consistent policy for teachers' salaries, incentives and increments. Reward and penalty should be awarded with justice.

- Teacher may be given a proper status by involving them in decision making, particularly in academic affairs and to some extent in administrative issues.
- Teachers may be provided with an environment of mutual support, satisfaction and motivation. There may be no unhealthy criticism, injustice, blaming and favouritism.
- The work pressure of teachers may be reduced through flexible deadlines, non-threatening environment, job security
- Female teachers usually feel more pressure, anxiety and insecurity. So they may be provided with pressure free and secure environment.
- The entire staff member including teaching and non-teaching personnel may be registered with worker welfare board in order to get some economic and social benefits and get satisfaction.

References

- Banal, C. L., & Ortega-Dela, R. A. (2022). Teachers' resilience in facing workload adversities in times of pandemic: The case of private school teachers in a developing country. *Indonesian Journal of Social Science*, 14(1), 36-51.
- Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education, Peshawar. (2023). *Gazette result - 2023*. BISE Peshawar.
- Collie, R. J., Shapka, J. D., & Perry, N. E. (2012). School climate and social-emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and teaching efficacy. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(4), 1189-1204.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029356>
- Demerouti, E., & Bakker, A. B. (2011). The job demands-resources model: Challenges for future research. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 37(2), 1-9.
<https://doi.org/10.4102/sajip.v37i2.974>
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499-

512. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.86.3.499>
- Dinham, S., & Scott, C. (1998). A three domain model of teacher and school executive career satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 36(4), 362-378. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578239810211545>
- Greenberg, M. T., Brown, J. L., & Abenavoli, R. M. (2016). *Teacher stress and health: Effects on teachers, students, and schools*. The Pennsylvania State University.
- Gupta, M., & Rani, S. (2014). Burnout: A serious problem prevalent among teachers in the present times. *Journal of Education & Research*, 4(1), 76-88.
- Hakanen, J. J., Bakker, A. B., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2006). Burnout and work engagement among teachers. *Journal of School Psychology*, 43(6), 495-513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2005.11.001>
- Jain, A. K., & Cooper, C. L. (2012). Stress and organizational citizenship behaviours in Indian business process outsourcing organizations. *IIMB Management Review*, 24(3), 155-163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2012.06.004>
- Kyriacou, C. (2001). Teacher stress: Directions for future research. *Educational Review*, 53(1), 27-35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131910120033628>
- Renshaw, T. L., & Cooper, B. R. (2006). Stress and coping of public school teachers. In J. L. R. Z. D. Gentry (Ed.), *Handbook of stress in the occupations* (pp. 379-396). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Shah, F., Azman, A., & Singh, P. S. J. (2023). Stress, stressors, and coping strategies of female private school teachers to deal with occupational stress. *Asian Social Work Journal*, 8(1), e00241. <https://doi.org/10.47405/aswj.v8i1.246>

